

OPTIMIZING PRECONCEPTION PREPARATION FOR WOMEN WITH CHRONIC
HYPOPLASTIC ENDOMETRITIS

Kurbaniyazova Feruza

Samarkand State Medical University

Assistant of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology No. 1.

Sodikova Ozoda

Student of Samarkand State Medical University!

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10829371>

Abstract. *The purpose of the study is to justify the refusal of antibacterial therapy for the hypoplastic variant of chronic endometritis.*

Key words: *hypoplastic variant of chronic endometritis; placental hydrolyzate; diosmin 600; antibiotic therapy.*

ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ПОДГОТОВКИ К ЗАЧАТИЮ ЖЕНЩИН С
ХРОНИЧЕСКИМ ГИПОПЛАСТИЧЕСКИМ ЭНДОМЕТРИТОМ

Аннотация. *Цель исследования – обосновать отказ от антибактериальной терапии при гипопластическом варианте хронического эндометрита.*

Ключевые слова: *гипопластический вариант хронического эндометрита; плацентарный гидролизат; диосмин 600; антибиотикотерапия.*

Materials and methods.

The study included 116 patients with a difficult reproductive history (infertility, pregnancy, unsuccessful attempts at IVF and PE), who after a comprehensive examination (hysteroscopy, morphology and immunohistochemistry of the endometrium) were diagnosed with the hypoplastic variant of chronic endometritis.

The work was carried out in two stages. At the first stage, the autoimmune genesis of the disease was proven in the examination of patients. In the second stage, patients were divided into two groups - the main group (84 women) and the control group (32 women). In the control group, patients received traditional antibacterial therapy with simultaneous use of trophotropic agents (placental hydrolyzate - Laennec, phlebotonic diosmin 600). In the main group, we avoided antibacterial drugs, including only immunomodulating trophotropic drugs in therapy.

116 patients with hypoplastic variant of chronic endometritis, history of reproductive failure (repeated pregnancy loss, infertility, multiple attempts at IVF and ET) were examined and treated. The age of the women participating in the study was 26-41 years old, with an average of

31.3 ± 4.7 years. The diagnosis of chronic endometritis was determined morphologically. All patients underwent pelvic ultrasound to determine the type of endometritis, and Doppler ultrasound was performed to assess blood flow. In addition, hysteroscopic, immunohistochemical and bacteriological examination of the endometrium was used, systemic and local immune indicators were also evaluated.

Currently, there are two approaches to solving the problem of chronic endometritis treatment [1-4]. Some researchers consider this disease to be a pure inflammatory reaction that requires antibiotic therapy [2, 3, 5, 6], while others consider chronic endometritis to be an autoimmune process in which the use of antibiotics is unreasonable [7-9].

Undoubtedly, chronic endometritis often occurs in women with reproductive incapacity (loss of normal pregnancy, infertility, multiple unsuccessful attempts at IVF and PE), and therefore it is necessary to identify and correct it at the stage of preparation for conception. Urgent task of modern reproductive medicine [6, 10].

It is known that the greatest difficulty in restoring the endometrium is the hypoplastic variant of chronic endometritis, in which the thickness of the endometrium in the "implantation window" remains less than 8 mm. The literature [3, 4, 9] contains information about attempts to restore the endometrium by introducing immunomodulators, stem cells, and physical therapy [2, 5]. The authors studied the possibilities of treating the hypoplastic variant of chronic endometritis without the use of antibacterial therapy.

Results. It was found that traditional therapy does not affect the cell composition of the endometrium (CD3 +, CD4 +, CD8 +, CD56 +) and humoral immunity indicators. When using only immunomodulating trophotropic agents, positive trends were noted in the normalization of the cell composition of the endometrium, the level of autoimmunity (IgG) decreased, the blood supply to the myometrium and endometrium improved, and an increase in the thickness of the endometrium was noted.

Summary. The hypoplastic variant of chronic endometritis is a typical autoimmune process in which antibiotics are useless. At the same time, positive trends in the use of immunomodulating trophotropic agents showed the feasibility of their introduction.

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of the combined use of immunomodulators and phlebotonics in the treatment of hypoplastic chronic endometritis and justify the need to abandon antibacterial therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Курбаниязова, В. Э., Н. А. Ахтамова, and Ш. М. Хамидова. "Интенсивное восстановление женщин репродуктивного возраста перенесших операцию Кесарево сечение." Проблемы биологии и медицины 4 (2019): 53-55.
2. Курбаниязова Венера Энверовна Ранняя реабилитация женщин, перенесших кесарево сечение, и оптимизация ведения последующих родов // Достижения науки и образования. 2020. №2 (56). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rannaya-reabilitatsiya-zhenshin-perenessih-kesarevo-sechenie-i-optimizatsiya-vedeniya-posleduyuschih-rodov> (дата обращения: 24.04.2023).
3. Тилявова, С., et al. "Акушерские аспекты нарушений мочеиспускания у женщин." Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины 4, 1 (85) (2015): 173-175.
4. Курбаниязова, В. Э., and Д. Д. Камалова. "Эффективная контрацепция после кесарева сечения." Неделя науки 2015. 2015.
5. Закирова, Н., et al. "Акушерские и перинатальные исходы беременности при артериальной гипотензии." Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины 1 (93) (2017): 195-197.
6. Kurbaniyazova, V. E., and K. D. Rakhimovna. "Prospects for the rehabilitation of women under cesarian section." European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine 7.3 (2020): 4385-4398.
7. Курбаниязова Венера Энверовна, Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна РЕАЛИИ ВРЕМЕНИ. РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ЖЕНЩИН С РУБЦОМ НА МАТКЕ // Вестник науки и образования. 2020. №23-1 (101). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/realii-vremeni-reabilitatsiya-zhenshin-s-rubtsom-na-matke> (дата обращения: 24.04.2023).
8. V. Kurbaniyazova CESAREAN SECTION: INSTRUCTIONS, DISADVANTAGES AND ADVANTAGES, COMPLICATIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS // SAI. 2023. №D2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/cesarean-section-instructions-disadvantages-and-advantages-complications-recommendations> (дата обращения: 24.04.2023).
9. Enverovna, Kurbaniyazova Venera. "Histological analysis of the state of the scar after operational delivery." Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research 11.10 (2022): 149-155.
10. Курбаниязова, Венера Энверовна. "CLINICAL, ECHOGRAPHIC, MORPHOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING A WELL-FOUNDED SCAR ON THE UTERUS AFTER CESAREAN SECTION." УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ SPECIAL 1 (2021).

11. Курбаниязова, Венера Энверовна. "CLINICAL, ECHOGRAPHIC, MORPHOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING A WELL-FOUNDED SCAR ON THE UTERUS AFTER CESAREAN SECTION." УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ SPECIAL 1 (2021).
12. Farrukh S. ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 8. – С. 493-499. ★
13. Сайинаев, Ф. К., Курбаниязова, Ф. З., Аззамов, Ж. А., & Вохидов, Ж. Ж. (2018). МИНИИНВАЗИВНЫЕ ВМЕШАТЕЛЬСТВА В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ВАРИКОЗНОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ НИЖНИХ КОНЕЧНОСТЕЙ. In Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке (pp. 436-438).
14. Саидмуратов, К. Б., Анарбаев, С. А., Курбаниязова, Ф. З., Аззамов, Ж. А., & Вохидов, Ж. Ж. (2018). ХИРУРГИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД К ЛЕЧЕНИЮ БОЛЬНЫХ С ПОСТТРАВМАТИЧЕСКИМИ РУБЦОВЫМИ СТРИКТУРАМИ МАГИСТРАЛЬНЫХ ЖЕЛЧНЫХ ПРОТОКОВ. In Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке (pp. 434-436).
15. Арзиев, И. А., Алиева, С. З., Курбаниязова, Ф. З., Шамсиева, Д. А., Аззамов, Ж. А., & Олимжонova, Ф. О. (2018). ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВАРИКОЗНОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ НИЖНИХ КОНЕЧНОСТЕЙ. In Завадские чтения (pp. 33-35).
16. Зайниев, А. Ф., Абдурахмонов, Д. Ш., Курбаниязова, Ф. З., & Курбаниязов, З. Б. (2019). Определение хирургической тактики при токсическом зобе. In Медико-биологические, клинические и социальные вопросы здоровья и патологии человека (pp. 136-137).
17. Курбаниязов, З. Б., Рахманов, К. Э., Давлатов, С. С., Курбаниязова, Ф. З., Аззамов, Ж. А., & Олимжонova, Ф. О. (2018). Совершенствование хирургического лечения эхинококкоза легких. Актуальные вопросы современной пульмонологии. Ма, 107.